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Microbial Diversity And Crude Oil Degrading Potential Of Bacteria From Hydrocarbon Polluted Water In The Niger Delta Region Of Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Widespread use and release of crude oil contaminates the ecosystem with negative effects on human and environmental health which raises concern for a clean-up process. The current study determines the microbial diversity and crude oil degrading potential of bacteria from hydrocarbon polluted water in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. The ability to degrade the hydrocarbons was measured indirectly by determination of density of viable cells produced, optical density and changes in pH of culture medium; and directly by estimating the rate of degradation of petroleum hydrocarbon contents in crude oil using Gas chromatography coupled with Flame Ionization Detector (FID). The results obtained from the bacteriological analysis of B-dere water using culture dependent technique revealed the presence of the 10 bacteria: *Salmonella* sp, *Bacillus* sp, *Enterobacter* sp, *Pseudomonas* sp, *Citrobacter* sp, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Chromatium* sp, *Kliebsiella* sp, *Escherichia coli* and *Vibrio* sp. Metagenomic technique revealed the presence of 1086 species which spread across 25 phyla, 575 genera and 1086 species. The results for heavy metals in polluted water were 1.095, <0.001, 0.08, 0.068, 0.149, 0.032, and 0.046 (mg/l) respectively for Arsenic, Cadmium, Nickel, Copper, Lead, Iron and Zinc. Preliminary screening of B-Dere water Hydrocarbonoclastic bacteria isolates revealed that among the 10 bacterial isolates detected, 2 bacterial isolates (*Bacillus* and *Pseudomonas* sp) exhibited a strong ability to utilize crude oil. The high rate of hydrocarbon degradation exhibited by bacterial consortium of *Bacillus* and *Pseudomonas* and single species augmented medium implies that bioaugmentation can be harnessed for bioremediation purposes in this study site.

Keywords: *Bacterial, Biodiversity, Biodegradation, Crude oil, Environmental contamination,*

INTRODUCTION

Crude oil is the main energy resources for modern industry (Sorrell *et al.*, 2010). Basically, a mixture of hydrocarbons [paraffinic (saturated), naphthenic (unsaturated) or aromatics (ring structured) (Yasin *et al.*, 2013, Odebunmi *et al.*, 2002, Odeyemi & Ogunseitan, 1985), chlorinated and nitroaromatic compounds

of which when released into the environment due to crude oil spillage (Holliger *et al.*, 1997) are detrimental to both ecosystem and human health (Ordinioha & Sawyer, 2010; Sam *et al.*, 2016).

Nigeria is one of the major crude oil producing nations in the world. Crude oil and natural gas activities are the main contributors of Nigerian foreign earning (Izah & Ohimain, 2015). As over 80% of Nigerian budgets are financed from the proceeds from sales of crude oil. This crude oil is domiciled in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria comprising of nine states including Ondo in the Southwest geopolitical zone, Edo, Delta, Bayelsa, Rivers, Akwa-Ibom and Cross Rivers in the South-South region, and Abia and Imo in the South East region of Nigeria.

Large parts of the dry lands and wetlands within the Niger Delta region are chronically affected by crude oil spills, and rapidly distributed with the aid of tides, floods, and rains; thus, several meters of soils and ground waters have experienced contamination which could result to public health deterioration (Moffat & Linden, 1995; Ana *et al.*, 2009; Mmom & Arokoyu, 2010; UNEP, 2011). Widespread use and release of crude oil contaminates the ecosystem with negative effects on human and environmental health which raises concern for a clean-up process. The deleterious effects of crude oil contamination of the environment include biodiversity loss, increase in cancer cases, mutations and birth defects, reduced soil fertility and plant growth response, heavy metal accumulation in soil and trophic transfer (Henze *et al.*, 2002).

Awareness of the detrimental impact of hydrocarbon pollution necessitate the search for biological techniques to restore the environment to a pristine state, and Bioremediation of contaminated environment which involves the effective use of adapted microbial species to the prevailing environmental conditions is one of the cheapest techniques for restoration of polluted ecosystem. The current study determines the microbial diversity and crude oil degrading potential of bacteria from hydrocarbon polluted water in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection

Brackish water samples of flowing water were collected within B-Dere community in Gokana Local Government Area, Rivers State, South-South, Nigeria. The hydrocarbon contaminated water was collected using sterile 1000ml plastic bottles at a depth of about 10cm (Near-surface) in the month of January 2019. The samples were within two hours transported to the Microbiology laboratory in an ice chest, and the samples were refrigerated at 4°C prior to microbiological analysis.

Heavy Metal Content using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (AAS)

10ml of each sample was contacted with 10ml of concentrated HCL and Nitric acids mixture in the ratio 3:1 (i.e., 7.5ml HCL and 2.5ml HNO₃). The mixture was swirled and kept in the fume cupboard. The samples were digested on hot plate stirrer at 600C until cessation of white fumes.

After cooling for 10 minutes, 10ml of deionized water was added and filtered using separating filter paper. The filtrates were analyzed using atomic absorption spectrophotometer. Heavy metal absorbance detected at various wavelengths were mainly for Chromium, Cadmium, Nickel, Lead, Zinc, Copper, Manganese and Iron.

Mineral Salt Agar Composition

Mineral salt agar used for this study was made up of NaCl – 10g/L, MgSO₄.7H₂O – 0.42g/L, KCl – 0.29g/L, KH₂PO₄ – 0.83g/L, NO₂HPO₄ – 1.125g/L, NaNO₃ – 0.42g/L, Agar – 20g/L, Crude oil – 1% V/V and distilled water. The mixture was autoclaved at 121°C at 15 Psi for 15 minutes.

Hydrocarbon Utilizing Bacteria determination

The water samples were serially diluted following the method previously described by Pepper & Gerba, (2005) and Benson, (2002). Ketoconazole (0.1ml) solution was added to bacterial plates to inhibit fungal isolates before the Mineral salt agar was poured. The vapour phase method (Mills *et al.*, 1978) was employed for determination of hydrocarbon degrading bacteria. A piece of Whitman filter paper which had been previously soaked in Bonny Light crude oil was then picked using a pair of forceps and placed in the lid of each Petri-dish. Culture plates were incubated in inverted position at 28°C – 30°C for 7 days for hydrocarbon utilizing bacteria. The resultant colonies were isolated into pure culture and identified by

the biochemical tests previously described by Cheesbrough (2009) and Benson (2002). The characteristics of the isolates were compared with those of known taxa following the guide provided by Cheesbrough (2009) and Bergey's Manual of Determinative Bacteriology

Constituents of Experimental Group

The experimental group had different composition as summarized below:

- (1) Sample A: Mineral salt agar (MSA) (500ml) + crude oil (2ml) + 1ml each of isolates 1 (*Bacillus* species) and 2 (*Pseudomonas* species).
- (2) Sample B: MSA (500ml) + crude oil (2ml) + Isolate 1 (1ml)
- (3) Sample C: MSA (500ml) + crude oil (2ml) + Isolates 2 (1ml)
- (4) Sample D: MSA (500ml) + crude oil 2ml (Control)

The experiment lasted for 21 days, and the samples were obtained at 7 days intervals. Hence the samples were obtained and analysed for total petroleum hydrocarbon between 0, 7, 14, 21, 28, 35, 42, 49 and 56 (days).

Total petroleum hydrocarbon determination using gas chromatography

Gas chromatography flame ionization detector (GCFID) was used for TPH analysis, method employed was USEPA 8015.

The sample extract was passed through glass wool in the presence of anhydrous sodium sulphate. The extracted samples were then placed in vials in an auto sampler of a calibrated GCFID which has built in method for TPH analysis.

Efficiency of Biostimulation (%) in MSA

The efficiency of biostimulation of crude oil was calculated following the method previously used by Zahed *et al.* (2011). Biostimulation Efficiency (B.E) % was calculated at 0, 7, 14, 21, 28, 35, 42, 49 and

56 (days). Efficiency of Biostimulation (%) = $\frac{TPH_0 - TPH_c}{TPA_0} \times 100$

Where TPH_{A_0} is the medium containing the various organisms at day 0, while TPH_c is the Concentration of TPH in the medium at day 56.

Statistical analysis

IBM SPSS version 20 was used for the statistical analysis. The data obtained was presented as mean \pm standard error. Two-way analysis of variance (Two-way Anova) was carried out at $p=0.05$, and turkey honesty significant difference was used to discern the source of the observed deviation. The graphical charts were plotted using GraphPad prism 5.

RESULTS

3.1. Determination of the physicochemical attributes of hydrocarbon polluted water from B.Dere in Ogoni land

The physicochemical properties of B-Dere polluted water are presented in Table 3.1. The results revealed a slightly acidic water (pH of 5.84) characterized with high level of conductivity (4840 μ S/cm). The total Suspended Solids was 1.5 mg/l which was lower than both the NUPRC target value and NUPRC Intervention Value. The dissolved oxygen and chemical oxygen demand were 3.83 and 6.668mg/l, respectively. The total petroleum hydrocarbon value (1572 μ g/l) in the water sample was higher than the recommended standard by both the NUPRC target value (50) and NUPRC Intervention Value (600).

3.2. Determination of the Heavy metal concentration of crude oil polluted water from B. Dere

The concentration of the heavy metals in the polluted water is presented in Table 3.2. The value of the extractable heavy metals in polluted water were 1.095, <0.001, 0.08, 0.068, 0.149, 0.032, and 0.046 (mg/l) for Arsenic, Cadmium, Nickel, Copper, Lead, Iron and Zinc. The values recorded for Nickel, Arsenic and lead were higher and calls for concern.

Table 3.1: Physicochemical properties

Parameter	Polluted Water	NUPRC Target Value	NUPRC Intervention Value
pH	5.84	6.5 - 9.5	7 - 8.5
Electrical Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	4840	NA	NA
Total Suspended Solids (mg/l)	1.5	500	1500
Turbidity (NTU)	1	NA	NA
Dissolved Oxygen (mg/l)	3.83	NA	NA
Chemical Oxygen Demand (mg/l)	6.668	NA	NA
Total hydrocarbon content ($\mu\text{g}/\text{l}$)	1572	50	600

Table 3.2: Heavy metal concentration of polluted water

Heavy metal	Concentration (mg/l)	NSDWQ, 2007	WHO
Arsenic	1.095	0.01	0.01
Cadmium	<0.001	0.003	
Copper	0.068	1.0	2.0
Iron	0.149	0.3	0.05-0.3
Lead	0.032	0.01	0.01
Nickel	0.08	0.01	0.07
Zinc	0.046	5.0	3.0

Microbial load of the crude oil polluted water sample

The results presented in Tables 3.3 revealed the microbiological properties recorded for Dere polluted water. The results have revealed a rich microbial assemblage and diversity of the polluted water sample. The data derived have shown that total heterotrophic bacterial density was 2.1×10^7 (CFU/ml) while the hydrocarbon degrading bacteria (HDC) was 9.8×10^2 (CFU/ml). A significant difference was observed between both THBC and HDC ($p < 0.05$) (Tables 3.3).

Table 3.3: Microbial counts of B.Dere polluted water

Bacterial group	Count (CFU/ml)
Total heterotrophic bacteria (THB)	2.1×10^7
Hydrocarbon degrading bacteria (HDB)	9.8×10^2

Characterization and identification of bacterial isolates

Bacterial isolates were characterized and identified based on their morphological, microscopy and biochemical characteristics (Table 4.4). Microscopic observation revealed 7 Gram-negative and 3 Gram-positive bacterial isolates. The identified bacterial species include *Salmonella* sp, *Bacillus* sp., *Enterobacter* sp., *Pseudomonas* sp., *Citrobacter* sp., *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Chromatium* sp., *Klebsiella* sp. and *Escherichia coli*.

Table 3.4: Morphological, cultural and biochemical characteristics of isolates from water sample

Gram Reaction	Shape	Catalase	Coagulase	Motility	MR	VP	Indole	Starch Hydrolysis	Citrate	Urease	H ₂ S	Spore Stain	Glucose	Sugar Fermentation			
														Lactose	Sucrose	Fructose	
-ve	Medium rods	+	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	AG	A	-	AG	<i>Salmonella</i> sp
+ve	Thick rod	+	-	+	-	+	ND	+	+	+	+	+	AG	-	A	AG	<i>Bacillus</i> sp
-ve	Rod	+	+	+	-	+	-	ND	+	-	-	ND	AG	+	+	ND	<i>Enterobacter</i> sp
-ve	Rod	+	ND	+	ND	-	-	ND	ND	-	ND	ND	-	+	ND	ND	<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp
-ve	Rod	+	ND	ND	+	-	-	ND	+	ND	ND	ND	±	ND	ND	+	<i>Citrobacter</i> sp
+ve	Cocci in cluster	+	+	-	-	+	ND	-	-	-	-	ND	A	-	A	A	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
+ve	Plemorphic rod	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	AG	A	A	AG	<i>Chromatium</i> sp
-ve	Tiny short rods	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	ND	AG	AG	AG	AG	<i>Klebsiella</i> sp
-ve	Curved rod	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	AG	AG	A	AG	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
-ve	Curved rod	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	+	-	A	AG	A	AG	<i>Vibrio</i> sp

Hydrocarbon Utilization Potential of Bacteria Isolated from polluted water

The hydrocarbonoclastic potential of bacteria isolated from the polluted water are presented in Table 4.5. The screening test showed that most of the bacteria encountered in the B- Dere water *Vibrio* sp had a varying ability to utilize hydrocarbons. Among the isolates, *Salmonella* sp, *Escherichia coli*, and *Enterobacter* sp exhibited weak growth on the oil medium at the end of 14 days incubation. *Citrobacter* sp and *Klebsiella* sp encountered in the ecosystem demonstrated moderate oil degrading capabilities. However, *Pseudomonas* sp and *Bacillus* sp had the best ability to utilize crude oil in the degradation studies.

Table 3.5: Hydrocarbonoclastic potential of bacteria isolated from B-Dere polluted water

Isolate	Growth on crude oil after	
	7 days	Growth on crude oil after 14 days
<i>Salmonella</i> sp	-	+
<i>Bacillus</i> sp	++	+++
<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp	+++	+++
<i>Enterobacter</i> sp	+	+
<i>Citrobacter</i> sp	++	++
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	-	+
<i>Chromatium</i> sp	-	++
<i>Klebsiella</i> sp	+	++
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	-	+
<i>Vibrio</i> sp	-	+

Key: - = no growth, + = 1-5mm (weak) ++ = 6-10 mm (moderate), +++ = 11-15 mm (strong), ++++ = 16-20 mm (strongest)

Bacterial and archaeal Community in the water sample using 16 S Metagenomics

In the study, water sample was sequenced for 16S rRNA amplification, resulting in a total of 531,927 sequenced reads. The sequencing of the PCR product using universal bacterial primers yielded 529,320 bacterial and 20 archaeal communities. The taxonomic profiles revealed 2,587 microorganisms (0.486%) that are yet to be classified. Proteobacteria, Tenericutes, Bacteroidetes, Planctomycetes, Firmicutes, Chlamydiae, Nitrospirae, Chloroflexi, Cyanobacteria, Actinobacteria, Chlorobi, Spirochaetes, Verrucomicrobia, Acidobacteria, Thermi, Caldithrix, Thermodesulfobacteria, Deferribacteres, Synergistetes, Thermotogae, Fibrobacteres, Caldiserica, Fusobacteria, Armatimonadetes and Chrysiogenetes were the bacterial phyla identified in this study. The top bacterial phyla with relative abundance greater 1 % were Proteobacteria (79.22 %), Bacteroidetes (3.56 %), Tenericutes (3.05 %), Planctomycetes (3.23 %) Firmicutes (2.07 %) and Chlamydiae (1.11). Abundance of the phyla Fusobacteria (0.0006 %), Armatimonadetes (0.0002 %) and Chrysiogenetes (0.0002 %) were less than 0.001%.

Precisely 575 bacterial genera were detected in this study, however the different genus varied in number of their relative abundance. About seven (7) genera (*Shewanella*, *Acinetobacter*, *Enterobacter*, *Mycoplasma*, *Wautersiella*, *Desulfonatronum* and *Planctomyces*) were the most dominant in the sample. Overall, *Shewanella* was the most prominent with 90216 sequences read while 38.90 % of the bacterial genera detected are yet to be classified. Bacterial genera with relative abundance ≥ 1 % were *Shewanella* (17.04 %), *Acinetobacter* (9.37 %), *Enterobacter* (5.42 %), *Mycoplasma* (3.03 %), *Wautersiella* (2.19 %), *Desulfonatronum* (1.82 %) and *Planctomyces* (1.79 %).

Table 3.6: Distribution of sequence reads in water sample

Microbial group	No. of hits	Relative abundance
Bacteria	529320	99.510
Archaea	20	0.004
Unclassified	2587	0.486

DISCUSSION

The results for some of the physicochemical parameter of water sample obtained in this investigation varied with the set standard for World Health Organization (WHO) and Nigeria standard of drinking water quality (NSDWQ). The finding is consistent with the report by Ganabel *et al.*, (2021), the physicochemical features of the receiving environment can be markedly modified by crude oil pollution. The pH is expressed as the reciprocal of the logarithm of the hydrogen ion activity and is used to quantify the activity of the hydrogen ion (H⁺). A slightly acidic (5.84) pH value as seen on Table 1 was observed. This finding suggests that various contaminations could be caused by petroleum product spills near or in water bodies. The pH value in this ecosystem was below the appropriate range for drinking water (6.5 to 8.5), optimal aquatic productivity (6.5 to 9.0) and but within the liveable range of 5.5 to 10. The influence of pH values on human physiological processes when consumed cannot be overstated, even though they have little impact on human domestic usage (Ganabel *et al.*, 2021). The measured pH value does not agree with the findings of Nkpaa *et al.*, (2013), who reported a pH of 6.61 in the same habitat. This discrepancy may be due to variations in the time of year or sampling or study methodology. The turbidity value (1 NTU) was relatively high. This may be explained by a range of materials from the many activities along the river, including organic waste and silt. These organic components frequently act as food for microorganisms, whilst the inorganic components promote the growth of algae (Ifelebuegu *et al.*, 2017).

Dissolved oxygen (DO) is essential to all aquatic life and varies with turbulence, atmospheric pressure, temperature and photosynthetic activity of plants and algae. The present investigation found that the dissolved oxygen level (3.83 mg/l) was below the tolerable limit (5.0 mg/l) for aquatic life in Ohio State, USA (APHA, 1998). The vast amounts of organic loads left behind by the massive deaths of aquatic life at the oil spill impacted site which requires high oxygen levels for decomposition and chemical oxidation could be the cause of the depletion of DO in B. Dere water. Some authors have previously reported similar findings of decreased DO in contaminated water (Udosen *et al.*, 2016; Andem *et al.*, 2012). In addition to being essential for aquatic life's survival, DO is a useful indicator of the level of freshness of water bodies such as rivers. Thus, DO from B-Dere is less than what is necessary for certain fish to survive. The low DO in the sample of water suggests a high level of pollution and its possible impact from both urban runoff from neighbouring towns and villages and crude oil pollution via oil operations.

Total suspended solids (TSS) of (1.5 mg/l mg/L) B-Dere water was found to be lower when compared to the maximum permissible limit of 1500 mg/l established by the World Health Organization (WHO 1997; Udosen *et al.*, 2016). One possible explanation for this could be the tidal impact of the river. TSS should typically be less than 25 mg/L to avoid having any negative effects on aquatic habitats (APHA, 1998; Nkpaa *et al.*, 2013). The healthy functioning of shellfish is impacted by TSS concentrations of more than 50 mg/l. Fisheries and water supply usage have established total suspended solid criteria of 50 mg/l and 25 mg/l, respectively (APHA, 1998).

Electrical conductivity (EC) is a measure of conducting ionic species in a sample solution. The high concentrations of conducting species, such as heavy metals, in the studied sample may have contributed to the degree of electrical conductivity (4840 μ S/cm) measured throughout the study period (Udosen *et al.*, 2016). Compared to the NSDWQ Standard of 1000 μ S/cm, the study's Electrical Conductivity measurement (4840 μ S/cm) was much higher. The recorded value was within the range of values for the freshwater systems of the Niger Delta, which have been reported to typically be between 20 and 1500 μ S/cm (Ifelebuegu *et al.*, 2017), but higher than values of 16.3 \pm 2.1-35.0 \pm 19 (μ S/cm) reported by Ganabel *et al.*, (2021) for hydrocarbon impacted communities, Rivers State

The surface water recorded a high hydrocarbon level of 1572 ($\mu\text{g/l}$). The findings show that petroleum products have significantly contaminated surface water in the study area. The fact that wastewater from oil exploration companies, oil spills, busted pipelines, and other cleaning operations in the vicinity are sent to an outlet along this water body may not be distant from these contaminations. This study supports the UNEP (2010) report, which examined an alarmingly high amount of TPH in the environment (2010). It has been previously shown that hydrocarbons can cause certain opportunistic bacteria, like *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*, to develop antibiotic resistance (Amala *et al.*, 2021).

Heavy metals concentration of water sample

Heavy metal pollution has gained significant attention, particularly in industrialized nations because of its toxicity, bioaccumulative, and persistent nature of heavy metals, in addition to being recognized as naturally occurring traces in the aquatic environment, heavy metals are also frequently referred to as environmental contaminants, especially when they come from human activity (Sharaf & Shehata, 2015). These heavy metals can be absorbed by living things, left behind in sediments, or remain in the water for a while (Santos *et al.*, 2005). The concentration of heavy metal obtained in our study exceeded the standard recommend by NSDWQ and WHO, except for Copper, Zinc and Cadmium that had a lower value of 0.068, 0.046 and <0.001 respectively, than the recommended standard set by WHO for Cu (2.00 mg/l) and Zn (3.00 mg/l) while for NSDWQ, for Cu is (1.00 mg/l), for Zn (5.00 mg/l) Cd (0.003 mg/l) and respectively.

The concentration of lead (Pb) was 0.032 which is 3.2 times higher than the standard recommended by NSDWQ. This was in line with research by Peretiemo-Clarke (2009), who found that Ogoni villages affected by hydrocarbons had greater levels of lead pollution from sediment. Similar high lead values (0.0336 ± 0.207) were also observed by Ganabel (2021) in water samples from Ogoni communities affected by hydrocarbons. Lead has serious health effects; elevated levels can harm kidneys in both adults and children, which puts those who drink water from this source at serious risk. The low cadmium value found is consistent with the findings of Chukwumati & Asiegbu's (2023) research, which suggested that cadmium is not a frequent heavy metal found in crude oil. The concentrations of Cd were far lower the 0.003 mg/l allowed by NSDWQ (2007) as permissible limit for Cd in water.

Arsenic concentration (1.095 mg/l) in the study area was 109.5 times higher than the recommended standard (0.01 mg/l) by NSDWQ and WHO. The concentration of arsenic may be related to petroleum product spills because of the research area's strong oil exploration activity. The pace at which arsenic compounds are eliminated from the body mostly determines their acute toxicity in humans (Akakuru *et al.*, 2017). According to Cheng (2016), there is no proof that arsenic is necessary for human health; rather, the acute toxicity of arsenic compounds in humans is mostly determined by how quickly the compounds are eliminated from the body.

The result indicate that Nickel showed very high contamination level in the water sample. This is of specific concern since it has a bioaccumulative, persistent and toxic characteristic. Ni is a highly toxic metal that has been connected to both environmental issues and health issues in humans. (Anyanwu *et al.*, 2023). High TPHs/HMs deposition in the study area is being caused by anthropogenic activities related to crude oil spills, industrial waste, and other processes (flooding, gas flaring, shipping activities, petroleum combustion, petroleum loading and off-loading). Furthermore, changes brought about by climate change will exacerbate these contaminant issues. This also demonstrates that high levels of Ni pollution have made the B-Dere a dangerous hotspot. Therefore, to meet the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations by 2030, priority should be given to ensuring that everyone has access to and sustains management of water and sanitation, with a focus on SDG-6 targets pertaining to water-use efficiency, quality, and management of water resources.

Microbiological studies

The distribution of microorganisms in the biosphere is determined by natural selection which impact interaction, but it is also dependent on environmental condition (Udofia *et al.*, 2022; Holly *et al.*, 2018). Owing to their diverse metabolic capacities, these microbes are involved in many crucial aspects of organic matter decomposition, mineralization, recycling, and transformation of element in aquatic environments. Aquatic ecosystems are dominated by microorganisms such as fungi, bacteria, archaea

and protists, which vary in biomass and abundance. Microorganisms show a wide range of metabolic functions and comprise a sizable and diverse pool of species. Several of them have important roles in biogeochemical processes (Udofia *et al.*, 2022), bioremediation (Umana *et al.*, 2017 a; b), and the regulation of water and sediment quality (Yu *et al.*, 2009). The existence of a variety of microorganisms that thrive in harsh environments and at high pollution concentrations contributes significantly to the field of bioremediation science. On the other hand, a variety of variables, including pollutant concentration, pH, moisture content, temperature, oxygen content, conductivity, nutrient availability and bioavailability, and the characteristics of the affected area, can reduce the rate of microbial growth and metabolism in affected areas (Umana *et al.* 2017 a, b).

The results of this study indicate that the microbial diversity in B-Dere water is highly diverse, encompassing both cultivable and non-cultivable species. This may be attributed to the fact that aquatic ecosystems serve as a sink for pollutants and waste from both the atmosphere and the lithosphere (Bashir *et al.*, 2020). The density of heterotrophic bacteria obtained from B -Dere water in the present study was slightly higher than values reported in Elechi Creek in Port Harcourt, Nigeria where the numbers ranged from 0.12×10^6 to 2.81×10^6 (CFU/ml) (Obire *et al.*, 2005) and 6.414 ± 0.078 (LogCFU/ml) and 6.394 ± 0.070 (LogCFU/ml) were observed at Ogobiri (upstream of River Igbedi) and Akaibiri (downstream of River Nun) respectively by Agedah *et al.*, (2015). It has been suggested that many of the advantages of multicellular life are available to microbes due to their heterotrophic activities. Microorganisms that interact with one another can engage in processes like co-metabolism, and varied/diverse populations are more resilient to environmental changes and can bounce back from adverse conditions faster than ecosystems with less diversity (Udofia *et al.*, 2022). The density of hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria (HDB) was 9.8×10^{-2} and was lower than THB counts. Lower HDB densities than THB were also noted by Udofia *et al.*, (2022). A culture-dependent approach identified a variety of bacterial species in the water, the majority of which had already been isolated by Mulamattathil *et al.*, (2014), Udofia *et al.*, (2022), and Adamu *et al.*, (2018). Enteric bacteria known as coliforms are utilized as markers to determine whether a bacterial pathogen is likely to be present in water. Although *Escherichia coli* (faecal coliform) by itself normally poses no threat to humans, its existence suggests the presence of faecal wastes that may contain pathogens (Fajri *et al.*, 2017).

The presence of *Salmonella*, *Escherichia coli* and *Vibrio* (coliform) in the water sample could have been caused by human influence and a warning about the potential for disease breakout should this polluted water be ingested by purpose or by accident. (Udofia *et al.*, 2022). The identified bacterial species (*Salmonella* sp, *Bacillus* sp, *Enterobacter* sp, *Pseudomonas* sp, *Citrobacter* sp, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Chromatium* sp, *Klebsiella* sp, *Escherichia coli* and *Vibrio* sp) exhibited varied level of hydrocarbon utilization. *Bacillus* sp exhibited the highest potential for crude oil utilization followed by *Pseudomonas* sp and were selected for biodegradation studies. The ability of *Pseudomonas* sp to utilize hydrocarbon can be linked to the fact that Gram-negative bacteria have porins in their cell walls, which aid in the uptake of some molecules by the cell or the ejection of others that may be hazardous, as well as plasmid-borne or chromosomal genes involved in hydrocarbon breakdown (Akpe *et al.*, 2013). It might also be connected to the *Pseudomonas* species' emulsifying and hemolytic action with crude oil, as described by Gomathy & Senthilkumar, (2012).

CONCLUSION

Hydrocarbon from petroleum products and its derivatives consist of many compounds which are mostly alkanes (which can either be linear or n-alkanes), branched (it has its carbon branched and can exist in diverse forms), and naphthenes (has its carbon atoms arranged in rings). The results of the study demonstrate that the presence of petroleum hydrocarbons at the study site changed its physicochemical characteristics and raised the content of heavy metals. The research indicates that B-dere has a very strong microbial diversity, suggesting a high potential for heterotrophic activity, even in the face of growing anthropogenic activities in and around the study area. Findings also showed that single bacteria, as well as a consortium of *Bacillus* and *Pseudomonas* species, have the necessary metabolic capacity to break down petroleum hydrocarbons in the water sample. Therefore, bioaugmentation with the

consortium and its isolates could be a useful inoculum for biotechnological applications aimed at cleaning up hydrocarbon-polluted environments.

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